

INFLUENCE OF THE SOVIET AUTHORITY ON SPIRITUAL AND CULTURAL LIFE IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

20-30 years of XX century period out of sight sorry we are in this all social life processes row cultural and spiritual the field itself special complexity, difficulty with that it was late sure we will be The Soviets authority and his dominant party whole in the country socialism system set up to reach own to them main the goal by doing puts they are, in this cultural of the field role individuality, without it a lot to something achieved that it won't be ok they understood. That's why soviet of the authorities initial years right from the start cultural construction process own supply and ideas based on to develop entered were.

Key words: Europe, Central Asia, Skobelov, modernism, cotton authoritarian, cultural revolution, proletariat dictatorship, V. Popov, attack, M. Kori-Yakubov, U. Egamberdiyev, H. Islamov, M. Kuznesova.

Tsarism of Central to Asia suppress of entry negative effect then It was Russian invaders the first in line people spiritual of culture development hindrance did National to inheritance has been relationship change it started. National pride and national pride feelings Rakhna goes to the village people to his mind Europe and Russian spirituality to absorb movement done Local the people are rich people and religious leaders to the hand taken from them using Russian to rule, invasion has been relationship to change, "cold" relations to warming, the concept of "invader". Instead of " help came", " culture take like "came". of concepts come in to come they wanted Even to sermons Russian of the king name adding to teach movement Ijildi. Europe science and technique mastering Russians themselves pressing received science and in the regions technique development to achieve (of course, own interests intended without) action they do As a result, Russian scientists societies, different different scientific publications to the body come, Central of Asia natural, economic maps structure goes, fauna and flora research it is muddy fossil mines places is determined. Russia industry for raw material as natural riches digging can be begins. Cotton monopoly reach for different different

irrigation branches and facilities will be built. In farming one so much shifts happened gives Of course, in the country Russian m spiritual invasion against different different actions to the body will come From these actions one enlightenment movement therefore, the second, his modern and one so much positive, public, especially young people not passing and fade away going national pride and national the soul to sharpen awareness to increase directed "combat" movement was Russian of the invaders Central Asia conquest reach national of intellectuals in his worldview one series of changes happen to the child take came.

In the early 20s come Uzbekistan in the area cultural of construction the most current of duties counted soviet education system formation works active starting from sent. The Soviets in Uzbekistan new education system to create road holds that's why intended main goals in the country people education joints development to find, to the whole People literacy reach, knowledge from the springs all of them full enjoy reach not but the most first of all, the children of the country to his mind, to his consciousness communist ideas and ideals deep absorb and that's it road with to themselves ear without stuttering service "believing-able" generation brought up adult deliver was.

"Cultural" of the councils revolution event of society all fronts in line science, culture, art education, higher education fields own to the trail put was. Education furnaces has been national the same for schools politics his own negative effect without transfer didn't stay Soviet of the authorities initial since years traditional education system no to do the climax was removed. State "dictatorship of the proletariat". there is all from the forces using the Soviet political leadership short lifetime inside in Turkestan chor empire installed education the basis of the system with no to do achieved. One of time in itself traditional to schools relatively administrative-repressive and economic measures was seen. Traditional school and madrasa as well new schools no to do with together soviet organs local population their children schools seriously attention did not give though, soviet study residences teacher personnel and necessary with funds provide opportunities to find received. For example, Shura education to the system suitable teacher of personnel quantitative growth provide wide to the road put in 1917 in Tashkent, Andijan, Samarkand, Kokand initial teachers who prepares short term courses organize done was of the 1920s to their heads come, that's it courses 3 thousand through local the nation and 802 Europeans teacher prepared.

That's it to emphasize on April 21, 1918 Russian intellectuals by Turkestan People University opened was. His the first rector V. Popov was Muslim People Dorylfun activity Shura government by stop from being placed after only Russian language knew local the nation representatives here it is that's it on the gallows higher

to study have to be possible was of 1926 September in the month Medium Asia party of committees wife girls departments employees in the presence of council was conducted and there women between take going things acceleration and him mandatory respectively to transfer decision done. It is mandatory the event was called "Attack". ie attack in style Women the problem solution to do policy superior be started. "Attack" first big successes to the hand introduced in 1927 to the spring 100 thousand a woman veil threw, 5 thousand a woman illiteracy finish in the courses study received, 5202 people a woman region, city, district to the courts people consultants by doing were elected. "Attack" action original purpose only burqa from throwing consists of it's not was. His main purpose women social work to issue wide attraction reach was that's it on purpose in Uzbekistan and to him next door in republics one series women examples organize done. "Attack" company in the process serious to shortcomings road was put Most first of all this event rush with, Uzbek to the people special national features, custom habits without being studied done increased. Comparison cultural inheritance denial reach policy Arabic writing Latin graphics replacement about his own decision on the contrary found. Of this the reason Soviets "cultural in growth technical to the feature have from obstacles one this backward transcription" and "traditional Arabic writing only religious" Muslim traditions point of view only from the point of view It is valuable "in Arabic of writing position to decrease movement they do This attitude with Uzbekistan III Congress of Communists (1927 November)" New Latin to the alphabet more more intense road with pass it is necessary, "he said and in 1929 Arabic writing Latin graphics changed. Because Medium Asia Arabs invasion from the 8th century starting from not only religious books, but all of science in the fields ten three century during created written cultural monuments, country population of action by doing came right sources mother that's it in writing created was For this reason this local The people from the culture, from the unique right Separately , Soviet to the mold by force put was in 1940 while Latin of graphics cyrillic with urgent replacement Uzbekistan population of knowledge level to grow, Uzbek of the language development negative effect showed. This error the illiterate number artificial growth cause released . But the most sad, spiritual life full Russified, all in places Uzbek language of possibilities limitation take came. In this place to say important Soviet Socialist statehood Uzbek the basic spiritual and moral of the people values suitable won't come was. Educational works are also scientific benefits reflection don't make was Mustabid system years in our republic literature with one in line national art also developed . In 1918, Hamza Fargona " Country "Savor" political troupe organize did M. Kori-Yakubov, U. Egamberdiyev, H. Islamov, M. Kuznesovalar that's it theater

swallows they were That's it year Mannon Uighur "Turon" society in Tashkent next to theater created. This is a group later on Country State example to the theater became. Theater the first actors Reputation Hidayatov, Muzaffar Muhamedov, Obid Jalilov, Fathulla Umarov, Saifi Olimov, Masuma Kariyeva, Bosit Kariyev, Ziya Said are. Mannon Uighur patriotism and enlightenment ideas with watered Fitrat, Ghulam Zafari, Cholpon, Qadiri. Azerbaijan playwright Hussein Javid his works staged by M. Kori-Yakubov during these years by the first being Uzbek People music ensemble organize done. In 1926 while surface came the first Uzbek state concert ethnographic to the ensemble famous Uzbek singer, actor, musicians attraction in 1929 his on the ground in Samarkand Uzbek state musical theater organize found. Exactly that's it in periods famous Uzbek performers on foreign tours were: Tamarakhonim and Snow Yakubovs Paris and grew up in Berlin (1925). success won in 1936 Uzbek state of the Philharmonic organize to be done performance of art known level to systematization basis it happened "cultural" of the Soviets revolution » event of society all aspects, especially science and culture very ideologizing his each one field cover took. Bolsheviks education initial and impressive weapon has been people education the first from the day ideology to the trail put for whole opportunity to work put. Political education in schools to the road to put and him by improving to go attention gave. It is known that the Bolsheviks ideology basically basically class struggle idea precedence did. Special to thinking has been each how attempt «class the enemy "resistance" was evaluated.

In the 20s and 30s strongman to the system against thought those who reported chase under get the climax took. The same that's it political activities such as "Group of 18", "Inogamovchilik", "Kasimovchilik" at the time knit issued was.

Uzbekistan President IA Karimov as noted, "Republic NKVD "Three". from 41 thousand in 1937-39 more person to prison 6 thousand 920 of them were taken shot thrown away was.¹"

So so, har how special the idea strength with suffocating, public arbitrariness and strength with Homeland loyal how many thousands people scratch thrown away strongman promotion decision found and increase went.

In the early 20s in Turkestan cultural construction works people economy destroyed has been and Bolsheviks on purpose starting from gave class struggle intensified complicated in the circumstances take went. In this period Turkestan cultural life inherent conflict, each other denial doer negative and positive of circumstances mutually struggle in the style of manifestation it happened Bolsheviks

1 Islam Karimov . High spirituality is invincible strength _ - T .: " Spirituality ", 2015.

monopoly recovered after division, chor government to politics monad respectively the soviets done increased cultural of politics priority direction nation, national identity understand important condition has been culture no do especially his national qualities break down to throw directed was. To the goal reach for soviet system installed initial from the day Bolsheviki party single, solitary dominant to the party rotation provide, to Bolshevism life has been all theory and to ideas against fight, their effect to lose directed politics take went.

Indeed, chor colonialism his own badass oppression, anger with our country, his sloppy people in the body indelible longing left their heart language bribes Arriving, impudent to deprivations receiver did. It belongs to our ancestors heart the world from time immemorial decorate them meaning and spirit supporting powered up What came is original spiritual values trouble find go to them in body and soul wave hit came national independence and man feelings little by little to stretch trying came. Our country soil to the blood belagan chor from the officers one General Skobelev, who was:

"The nation no to do for him shave a must not his culture, art, language no if you do, it's fast in between himself to recession occurs²," he said lewd words in vain not mentioned of course.

Here it is that's it ideological planned politics as a result councils during social and cultural institutions to the people service to do instead of, completely com Munist ideas promote doer to places converted. Form national, m flour socialist works Create demand while to each other similar, in essence shallow, one different to the mold put zorm a-zoraki written works to the creation the ground it happened Councils period socio-cultural in the activity local the conditions account not to get, Europe and to Russia special forms zorm a-zoraki stitching, cultural rneros and national traditions denial to break show, people creativity disregard such as many errors there is was. Councils during socio-cultural of activity the following from the forms more are used was: lively newspaper, oral magazine, rally at night, portrait evenings, concerts, lectures, agitsuds, demonstration, thematic nights ', and etc.

So even though he is strong system his own ideological restrictions, communist to the idea opposite has been to views uncompromising from being give up it didn't take long On the contrary, socio-economic stagnation years of political fanaticism more increased. Law issuer and performer power in the union as well as officially in the republic the soviets at his disposal was. Uzbekistan in 1950-1959 High Soviet Presidium Sh.R. Rashidov leadership did. Well, Soviet of the system complicated and

² Homeland culture history _ - T.: 1995.

very controversial years Uzbek people identity, ancient national culture and values save to stay movement did. But this easy it didn't take long It's on the way unique struggles and losses happen it happened Communist ideology local of the people national pride to break tried. The people national from culture, national from tradition distraction for "communism "and" developed like "socialism". fantastic beliefs thinking found them people mass to his mind absorb for all measures, tools and of methods used. But Uzbek people of these to all endure gave. Because the people in social and political life inevitable changes happen to be believe was.

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